

Title: Highly Skilled Women Reaching the Top: A Cost-free Achievement? Analyzing the Gender Promotion Gap in the Medical Profession.

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Abstract

This paper investigates the gender promotion gap in a particular highly skilled profession, that of physicians. The following analyses are based on a dataset of more than a thousand doctors working in Italy, a country in which hospitals play a central role in the national health care system. Given a three-step career ladder – first level, vice, and head - this research finds that women are 8% less likely than men to be promoted from the first level to vice, whereas no significant disadvantage is found in the promotion from vice to head. This suggests that the vertical segregation is due more to a sticky floors mechanism than to a glass ceiling effect. Moreover, no motherhood penalty occurs. Private organizations appear to be more gender equal than public ones and similar, albeit weaker, findings come from the analysis of the specialties, cautiously suggesting that the male-dominated area of surgery is more gender equal than the female-dominated area of medicine. These findings point out that women in highly skilled professions may encounter fewer obstacles to promotion than in the general labor market. Furthermore, they may encounter fewer obstacles within the most competitive organizations and specialty areas than across the profession in general. This is not, however, because of a greater number of opportunities, but because they represent a highly selected and career oriented population. These results shed light on the costs of such achievement for women, both in terms of effort and in terms of equality among women themselves.

Introduction

The medical profession has gone through a process of feminization of its work force in all major Western economies (Boulis and Jacobs 2010). Nonetheless, gender inequalities persist. Research shows that women earn less than men controlling for characteristics (Hoff 2004; Sasser 2005; Magnusson 2016; Ly et al. 2016; Roth 2016; Gaiaschi 2019). Other studies suggest how women tend to be concentrated in lower-paid specialties and practices, as well as in part-time work (Crompton and Lyonette 2011; Ku 2011; Pas et al. 2011). Similarly, they are less likely to hold leadership positions (McManus and Sproston 2000; Carnes et al. 2008; Spina and Vicarelli 2015; Abelson et al. 2016). Most scholarship to date has focused on *academic* medical careers. This study contributes to the literature by presenting original evidence from a case study of Italian *hospital* doctors, in which the consecutive steps along the promotional ladder have been closely tracked.

The analyses are based on a dataset of more than a thousand doctors working in five hospitals across

the Lombardy region in northern Italy. Analyzing the *promotion gap* in this context is interesting for two reasons. First, during a period in which the proportion of doctors working in hospitals in the United States is increasing (Kane 2017), studying intrahospital dynamics in a country such as Italy—in which hospitals play a central role in the country’s health care system—makes it possible to shed light on one possible evolution of the US health care system. In hospitals, career progression is affected by organizational dynamics, and rank is a key factor in determining salary, even more so than specialty or type of practice (Gaiaschi 2019). Second, the Lombardy health care system, which is known for being very competitive and for dispensing high quality standards of hospital care, is a mixed system, comprising both public and private providers. This makes it possible to analyze a highly selected, homogeneous population, but also to compare public and private organizations.

Using an online survey, the demographic characteristics of the physicians were collected, as well as details concerning their work and family structure. The data were analyzed through logistic regressions, with the aim of understanding in which steps along the career ladder obstacles to female advancement concentrate, and what the reasons for such obstacles might be.

Existing Literature on the Gender Promotion Gap

The study of gender inequalities in career progression among physicians parallels the wider debate concerning vertical segregation in the labor market in general. In analyzing vertical segregation, two aspects are of great importance in order to understand how it works and how to tackle it. The first aspect is *where* obstacles to promotion occur along the career ladder, that is at which rank they concentrate. The second aspect is *why* these obstacles appear at all.

Several metaphors have been used in relation to the first question: the “glass ceiling”, “sticky floors”, the “leaky pipeline”, and, less frequently, the “mid-level bottleneck”. The glass ceiling refers to the existence of an invisible barrier preventing women from reaching top positions (Federal Glass Ceiling Commission 1995). The strictest definition of this term implies that obstacles to women’s promotion are found at the end of the career ladder. Alternatively, interpreting the concept more broadly, it could be understood that obstacles increase all the way along the hierarchy, while being most challenging in the uppermost levels (Baxter and Wright 2000). In both cases, the final steps are the most problematic. Sticky floors, by contrast, describe a mechanism in which gender-based obstacles are stronger at the beginning of the ladder than at the end (Booth et al. 2003). As such, they suggest that the

first steps are crucial in determining future work outcomes. Scholars have also examined the role played by intermediate steps as pools pre-determining the candidates eligible for promotion into the top positions, thus suggesting the idea of a mid-level bottleneck (Yap and Konrad 2009). Sticky floors and the mid-level bottleneck are associated with the notion of “leaky pipeline”: if obstacles appear from the early through the intermediate ranks, the whole trajectory should be considered a pipeline “leaking” female talent from every step, and not only at the end. Often used to describe women’s dropping out of academia and science, the leaky pipeline metaphor (Alper 1993) emphasizes the idea that women’s low presence in top positions is the result of an accumulation of disadvantages (Merton 1968) all along the career ladder, and not just in the uppermost positions, as the metaphor of the glass ceiling might suggest.

Most studies of vertical segregation focus primarily on the gender-based promotion penalty in the labor market, either not taking the level at which promotion occurs into account (Booth et al. 2003), or only examining promotion to the top positions (Ransom and Oaxaca 2005). However, by ignoring the different levels of the career ladder, these studies cannot adequately test concepts such as sticky floors or glass ceiling. Such analyses require a scale in which the diverse levels within a work hierarchy are considered. To overcome this problem, many researchers look at wages attached to promotion (Cotter et al. 2001). Only few researchers have measured *variation* in the promotion gap *across the diverse steps* of a hierarchical scale. Among them, Baxter and Wright (2000) suggest that women’s chances of promotion are lower than those of their male counterparts at the lower rungs, rather than at the higher. Similar results—supporting the idea of sticky floors—stem from Hultin (2003), Bihagen and Ohls (2006), and Yap and Konrad (2009).

Alongside variation in the female promotion gap along the career ladder, a second important aspect is how to explain this gap in the first place. The contributions on this issue are many, and an efficient way of simplifying the debate is to distinguish between micro (individual), meso (organizational) and macro (institutional) factors (Bozzon et al. 2019)¹.

With respect to the individual level, borrowing vocabulary from the field of economics, it may be useful to distinguish between factors related, respectively, to the supply and demand sides of the labor market. The supply side refers to the workforce, specifically to differences in characteristics between men and women. The demand side refers to employer discrimination against women². On the supply side, two (interrelated) aspects are of major importance: gender differences in human capital, and in family responsibilities. Studies show that, despite recent gains, women still work, on average, fewer

hours than men, receive less on-the-job training, and have a less continuous work history due to maternity leave (for a comprehensive review, see Blau and Kahn 2017). This may explain their lower work outcomes, such pay or likelihood of promotion (Mincer and Polacheck 1974). At the same time, more recent studies show that the human capital component of inequalities has squeezed out, even more so for professionals at the higher end of the earning distribution (Goldin 2014). Concerning family responsibilities, studies have shown that, typically, men experience a marital and parental premium on their pay, whereas women are more likely to experience a penalty related to marriage and/or children (Budig and England 2001; Hodges and Budig 2010). However, findings regarding highly skilled professions are less clear-cut. For instance, some contributions regarding women in science reject, or at least call into question, the idea of a maternity penalty in relation to research productivity (Fox 2005) and promotion (Perna 2005) Furthermore, highly skilled women are less likely to be married, or to have children, than women in general, and yet they do not seem to be given more opportunities in career progression than women who are spouses or mothers (Bozzon et al., 2017).

When the promotion gap is not explained by supply-side factors, demand-side factors—namely employer discrimination—may offer further explanation. If men and women with *equal* characteristics are *differently* rewarded—in terms of recruitment, promotion, etc.—then discrimination is taking place. Discrimination occurs when *equivalent* men and women are *differently* evaluated in selection processes because of persistent gender biases that lead evaluators to believe men are more capable and competent than women (Valian 1999; Moss-Racusin 2012).

Individual factors (micro level) are not enough to explain gender inequalities in career progression. Meso and macro factors contribute as well. With respect to the meso level, many contributions have focused on the role of organizations—specifically, their culture and structure—in engendering inequalities. Feminist scholars have pointed out how organizational practices are inherently “gendered” as they promote the idea of an abstract worker, which is found actually to be a man, with a specific body, sexuality, and minimal family responsibilities (Acker 1990). In this vein, more recent contributions have shed light on gender inequality practices at the foundation of how recruitment and promotion criteria are constructed, and how this in turn generates systematic disadvantages for women (Van den Brink and Benschop 2011). Furthermore, women may experience exclusion from work-related social networks (McDonald 2011), resources (Ceci and Williams 2011), and mentoring (Fuchs et al. 2001). Gender homophily among male colleagues and superiors may lead to women being more isolated (McPherson et al. 2001) and this in turn, may reduce their opportunities for collaborations

(Zippel 2017), as well as negatively affecting their self-perception and motivation (Kelly and Grant 2012).

The organizational dimension is connected to the broader institutional context (macro level), which includes the structure of the labor market as well as (social, work and gender equality) policies. Several studies on the labor market have investigated the effects of horizontal segregation—unequal gender distribution between sectors, industries, occupations, etc.—on vertical segregation. Contributions on sectorial segregation suggest that the (female-dominated) public sector provides more standardized selection processes compared with the private sector (Rubery 2013). For this reason, gender biases may be less likely to occur. Likewise, heavily female-dominated occupations and industries report a higher share of female managers (Reskin and McBrier, 2000). Such considerations seem to support the idea that female-dominated sectors and occupations are more gender equal than male-dominated ones. Contrary to these findings, other studies have proved that women in female-dominated occupations may be subject to poorer career opportunities due to the way the career ladder is constructed: shorter and with closer rungs (England 1992; Deschacht 2017). At the same time, women working in male-dominated occupations may have better chances of promotion because they are highly selected (Hultin 2003).

Besides the labor market structure, public policies also contribute to shape gender (in)equality outcomes at the macro level. In this respect, an important strand of scholarship has focused on how different “welfare regimes” shape men and women’s career outcomes (Gornick and Meyers 2003; Jacobs and Gerson 2005). On this point, while some see state interventions as increasing women’s employment and wages (Gornick & Meyers 2003), others suggest that these interventions lead to trade-offs for women in the form of greater segregation (Mandel & Semyonov 2006; Pettit & Hook 2009). Further studies have downsized the trade-off argument, either by focusing on specific policies (Budig et al. 2016), or on subgroups of women from different classes and/or educational attainment levels (Grönlund and Magnusson 2016). Most scholars on this topic now agree that work-life policies have complex effects that vary according to the way in which the three “pillars” that constitute them (cash for care, care services, and working time policies) are designed: their weight and combination, the policy instruments used, and their aims and target (Solera and Musumeci 2017).

Research Design and Hypothesis

This paper investigates the mechanisms and determinants of vertical segregation among doctors through logistic regressions. The aim of this research is twofold: to analyze how the gender gap in promotion varies according to hierarchical level, and to identify its determinants.

With respect to the first issue, the female probability of promotion is measured at different levels. Within a three-step career ladder (first level, vice, and head), if, given equal characteristics, the female probability of being head instead of vice is worse than the female probability of being vice as opposed to first level, this should be considered evidence of a glass ceiling. By contrast, if the female probability of being vice as opposed to first level is worse than the female probability of being head instead of vice, this should be considered evidence of sticky floors.

After analyzing the variation in the gender gap along the career ladder, its determinants will be investigated. Virtually all regression-based methods distinguish between two components of the gender promotion gap (Grimshaw and Rubery 2002). The first component accounts for the part of the gap which is *explained* by women's and men's differences in observable characteristics, including human capital and job-related attributes (the "endowment" or "explained" component). The second component is the part of the gap persisting after controlling for observable characteristics. As such, it refers to employer discrimination and/or unobserved characteristics (the "remuneration" or "unexplained" component). Discrimination is what occurs when the same characteristic produces different "returns" (in terms of promotion) depending on whether it relates to men or women³.

This paper is focused on the mechanisms of discrimination by considering four hypotheses. First, working in private hospitals may be penalizing for women compared with the public sector (hypothesis 1). Second, women working in the female-dominated area of medicine may experience an advantage (hypothesis 2a) or, on the contrary, a disadvantage (hypothesis 2b) in promotion compared to women working in the male-dominated area of surgery. Third, being married (or living together) can entail positive returns for men and negative returns for women (hypothesis 3). Fourth, having children may negatively impact women's likelihood of promotion, while enhancing men's (hypothesis 4).

The Research Field

This research is based on a dataset collected through an online questionnaire sent to the physicians working in five hospitals in the Lombardy region of Italy between June 2014 and July 2015⁴. Out of the 2,205 doctors who received the questionnaire, 1,074 answered (a 48.7% response rate⁵). The hospitals were chosen to be as representative of the Lombardy health care system as possible, in that they varied by sector (three public, two private), vocation (three out of five are university hospitals), geography (two in the city of Milan, two in the province of Milan, and one in the province of Como), and size (ranging from around 300 doctors to about 900).

The Lombardy region is known for being one of the richest in Europe (GDP per capita is 36,000, vs the 29,200 average across Europe, EUROSTAT 2016). It outperforms the rest of Italy in terms of employment (68.9% vs 62.3%, EUROSTAT 2017a), female employment (58.7% vs 52.5%, EUROSTAT 2017b), and proportion of female physicians: 44.8% against 40.7% in the rest of Italy in 2015⁶ (OECD 2018). The region has a mixed health system that is extremely focused on hospital care, and in which one third of health care providers are private. At the same time, it guarantees the principles of universal coverage and equality of treatment, meaning that patients can access a private hospital for the same price as if they were visiting a public provider (services are reimbursed by the regional government) (Pelissero 2009). This has led to the creation of a system consisting of 130 providers (out of 1,070 in the whole country) and 18% of the total hospital beds in Italy (ISTAT 2017).

Analyzing the promotion gap in such a restricted population comes with both limitations and advantages. The population considered is not representative of the general labor market, since it represents a specific selection of highly skilled professionals. At the same time, it has the advantage of reducing the heterogeneity of characteristics, provided individuals are similar in terms of attributes. This reduces the potential bias in the estimations due to unobserved characteristics.

Models and Measures

In their criticism of Baxter and Wright's work (2000), Ferree and Purkayastha (2000) shed light on two problematic aspects linked to the use of logistic regressions in the study of vertical segregation. First, they argue, the analysis of female disadvantage across *adjacent* steps of the career ladder—from one rank to the next—is not enough to account for the mechanism of *cumulative* inequality. For example, if the level of female disadvantage is lower—or if it has disappeared completely— at the top level, this does not mean that women at the beginning of their careers have the same chance as men of reaching

the final steps. Second, since women are subjected to a sharper selection process than men as they move up the ladder, the ones that make it to the pool of candidates for promotion to the top level are likely to be more qualified than men in the same pool. In consequence, the (adjusted) probability of promotion is likely to be underestimated due to unobserved characteristics (productivity, motivation, ability, etc.).

Both these points has been taken into consideration. Adjacent level logistic regressions have been undertaken in parallel with non-adjacent level models, to account for the cumulative dimension of disadvantage. While the former analyzes the variation in the gender gap through all *consecutive* steps of the ladder, the latter captures the *cumulative* effect of early obstacles on the final positions. Moreover, the bias due to unobserved characteristics has been reduced, not only because focusing on a single profession makes it possible to control for heterogeneity, but because of the inclusion of a wide range of characteristics accounting for the quality of employees (educational credentials, training, non-paid activities, etc.).

The dependent variable is the position held by the respondent within a three-step career ladder (first level, vice, and head). This ladder has been created by harmonizing the different scales used by the various health care providers featured in this study, since the three public hospitals (Public 1, 2, and 3) have a six-step ladder in place, and the two private hospitals have a five (Private 2) and three-step (Private 1) ladder respectively. The first level of the new, harmonized scale groups together the first two ranks of the public hospitals and Private 2, all of which feature advancement from one rank to another based simply on seniority⁷. The vice level includes the three intermediate levels of the public hospitals, as well as the two intermediate levels of Private 2, in which doctors are responsible for a subunit and they manage their own teams. Here, promotion is based on a decision taken by their department head, with the approval of the hospital's board. Lastly, the head level is equal across all five original ladders. Physicians at this stage are responsible for a whole hospital unit and have reached the final rank of their career.

The results of these models are reported in Table 2. The first two models (M1 and M2) are adjacent levels regressions measuring the probability of being in level $n + 1$ compared to n . The first model measures the female coefficients of promotion from first level (n) to vice ($n + 1$), and the second from vice (n) to head ($n + 1$). In M1, the dataset is restricted to first level and vice doctors and rank is coded as a dummy variable, where 1 = vice and 0 = first level. In M2, the dataset is restricted to vice and head doctors, and rank is coded as a dummy variable where 1 = head and 0 = vice. In addition, a non-

adjacent level model (M3) accounts for the cumulative disadvantage in career progression by measuring the probability of being head (n + 2) rather than first level (n). The dataset is restricted to first level and head physicians and the dependent variable is coded as a dummy where 1 = head and 0 = first level.

The equation for the adjacent level models is:

$$\text{Log} [\text{Pr}(n + 1)/\text{Pr}(n)] = a + \sum \beta_{(n+1)i} X_i$$

The equation for the non-adjacent level model is:

$$\text{Log} [\text{Pr}(n + 2)/\text{Pr}(n)] = a + \sum \beta_{(n+2)i} X_i$$

where $\text{Pr}(n + 1)$ of the first model and $\text{Pr}(n + 2)$ of the second model are, respectively, the probability of being at level $n + 1$ or $n + 2$. $\text{Pr}(n)$ is the probability of being at level n , the coefficient β refers to the individual's (i) probability of being at level $n + 1$ or $n + 2$, X represents the covariates and a the intercept.

Finally, a group-level regression (M4) measures the probability of being head compared with being at the previous two levels. The first and vice levels are collapsed into a broader category (n). The dependent variable is a dummy where 1 = head and 0 = all other levels. This model makes it possible to increase the sample, as well as functioning as a reliability check: if the results are consistent across the different codifications, it increases confidence in the interpretation (Baxter and Wright 2000).

For each model, Table 2 indicates the unadjusted (first column) and adjusted (second column) gender gap in promotion, which is the coefficient of the independent variable "gender" (1 = women; 0 = men) without and with controls respectively. Table A1 of the Appendix shows the full adjusted models, including the coefficients of the control variables. Controls include human capital, as well as work and family characteristics. Human capital controls include educational credentials and postgraduate training. Educational credentials are operationalized through a dummy variable, assigning 1 to doctors who have graduated from medical school with a final grade of 105/110 or higher, and 0 to graduates with up to 104/110. Postgraduate training is operationalized through an interval variable accounting for the number of months spent training abroad since entry into the labor market. Work characteristics include individual (experience and work hours) and institutional (contract type, sector,

and specialty) attributes. Experience is an interval variable, accounting for the years of work since entry into the medical profession⁸. Work hours include both weekly salaried hours, which are the number of hours remunerated by the employer (the hospital), as well as weekly hours of private practice, which are the number of hours worked on a self-employed basis. Private practice (the so-called *libera professione*, literally “free profession”) is not covered by a doctor’s salary and can be conducted both in and outside the hospital in the individual’s own time, in accordance with an agreement signed with the hospital⁹. Contract type is operationalized through a dummy variable, based on whether the respondent has an open-ended contract (0) or a non-standard contract (1). Non-standard contracts include freelance contracts (“partita IVA”)¹⁰ and other atypical contracts: short-term contracts, research fellowships (“borsisti”) and contracts of collaboration (“co.co.co”). Sector is a dummy variable dependent upon whether the respondent works in a public (0) or private hospital (1). Specialty is a three-item categorical variable obtained by merging the four areas identified by the MIUR (Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research) in its specialties’ classification into three. The reference category covers the diagnostic and public health areas of specialty (0), the second item represents the medical area (1), and the third the surgical (2). The three items have been coded based on their gender composition: the reference (and first) category is gender-balanced, the second category is female-dominated and the third is male-dominated (see Table 1). Each MIUR area comprises a number of specialties from four to more than twenty. A detailed account of gender distribution by specialty can be found in Table B1 of the Appendix. Family characteristics include marital and parental status, with a dummy variable based on whether the respondent has a spouse or cohabiting partner (1) or not (0), and another based on whether he/she has children (1) or not (0). Work-life arrangements are provided by two interval variables: the former accounts for weekly hours dedicated to unpaid work, that is to care and domestic work, the latter for weekly hours of care and domestic activities outsourced to cleaning staff, babysitters, caregivers, etc.

The female coefficients in Table 2 are reported in logit (b) and in marginal effect (dy/dx). Marginal effects are an approximation, in percentage points, of how much a dependent variable increases/decreases for a unit change in the independent variable, or for a dummy changing from 0 to 1 (Williams 2012; Deschacht 2017)¹¹.

Once female promotional disadvantage has been determined along the stages of the hierarchy, its determinants are investigated by means of nested (Table 3) and interaction (Table 4) models. Nested models measure the contribution of gender differences in observable characteristics to the promotion

gap (analysis of the endowment or explained component of the gap, from now on also called “analysis of differential characteristics”), while interaction models make it possible to account for men’s and women’s different “returns” in terms of promotion for the same characteristics (analysis of the remuneration or unexplained component, from now on called “analysis of differential returns”).

Concerning the nested models, the aim of this technique is to analyze the variation in the coefficients of the independent variable gender once controls (or sets of controls) are progressively added into the model. Table 3 reports the female coefficients of promotion. The first specification reports the unadjusted gender promotion gap. Specifications 2-4 add work controls and, more specifically, work experience (second specification), work hours (third specification), sector, contract type and specialty (third specification). Specification 5 adds human capital controls (educational credentials and postgraduate training), specification 6 adds family characteristics (marital and parental status), while the seventh (and final) specification controls for work-life arrangements, that is hours of care and domestic work undertaken by the respondent (unpaid work) and hours of care and domestic work outsourced to others. The final specification also provides the adjusted gender promotion gap, that is the female disadvantage all else being equal, which should be ascribed to discrimination and/or unobserved factors.

Concerning the interaction models, two-way interaction terms—between the modifying variable gender and four independent variables (sector, specialty, marital status, parental status)—are included in models M1 (vice vs first level) and M3 (head vs first level) in order to test hypotheses 1-4. These models—M1_i and M3_i—are reported in Table A2 of the Appendix. Once these interaction terms have been added, the partial changes in the predicted margins (marginal effects) are computed. The reason for computing marginal effects (dy/dx) while ignoring the coefficients (b) of interaction terms is because the latter are substantially uninformative (see Brambor et al. 2005; Grotenhuis and Thijs 2015)¹². The marginal effects are reported in Table 4. Columns “Men” and “Women” measure the contribution on the dependent variable of a unit change of the independent variables for each value of the modifying variable gender. For example, with reference to the variable children, the marginal effect for men is the difference between the predicted margin or value (in the likelihood of promotion) for fathers and the predicted margin or value for men with no children. As such, it indicates the effect of fatherhood, and so the return that fathers experience compared to men with no children. Likewise, the marginal effect for women is the effect of motherhood, and therefore the return mothers experience compared to women with no children. Column “W-M” measures the contribution on the dependent

variable of a unit change of the modifying variable gender for each value of the independent variables. Given that gender is a dummy variable where 0 = men and 1 = women, “W-M” gives account of the gender promotion gap. Taking the example of the variable children, where children = 0, the marginal effect reports the promotion gap between women and men with no children. When children = 1, the marginal effect reports the difference in likelihood of promotion between mothers and fathers.

Figure 1 - The scissor diagram: men and women by rank (%)

Findings

Figure 1 reports a “scissor diagram”, pointing out that women are concentrated at the lower steps of the ladder, while men make up the majority at vice (62%) and head (76.5%) level¹³. Table 1 reports a list of characteristics, testing for significant gender differences using two-sample t-tests. Out of the 1,074 doctors who responded, 51.5% are male and 48.5% female. The proportion of women among respondents is slightly higher, both with respect to the population of the five hospitals (46.4%, difference not significant) and to the Lombardy region (44.8%).

Women respondents are, on average, younger than the men (48 vs 51 years old). They report fewer years of work experience (17 vs 21.6) and a lower gross annual income (63,000 vs 86,000 euro). The men and women are equally distributed across sectors, but not across contracts: women are more likely to have atypical contracts and less likely to have an open-ended contract. Moreover, 57% of female respondents work in the area of medicine, while only 16% are in the area of surgery, as opposed to 35% of male respondents.

Among the respondents, women have graduated from medical school with slightly better grades than men (108 vs 107) and are more likely to have received “honors” (51.5% vs 45%). The men report more on-the-job training (5.2 vs 2.8 months per year), and work three hours more per week, although this difference decreases to around one hour if only salaried work hours are considered.

With respect to family characteristics, men are more likely than women to be married (70.5% against 58%). Moreover, 61% of the women have children against 76% of the men. Among parents, there is a significant difference in the number of children: 1.5 for the men against 1 for the women. Lastly, women and men report a significant difference in weekly hours spent on care and domestic work, as well as in the number of hours of care and domestic work outsourced to others.

Table 1 – Mean differences by characteristic

Table 2 reports the results of four logistic models for each level of comparison, showing the female coefficients in logit (b) and marginal effect (dy/dx), without (first column) and with (second column) controls, thus accounting for the unadjusted and adjusted gender promotion gap respectively.

Considering the two adjacent level models, a significant unadjusted gender gap in promotion persists from first to vice level (M1: -15.8%), as well as from vice to head level (M2: -16.1%). After adding controls, the disadvantage in M2 disappears, while a significant disadvantage in M1 remains (-8.2%). These results make it possible to refute the glass ceiling hypothesis and suggest the existence of a sticky floors mechanism. Sticky floors negatively impact women's later careers, due to the mechanism of cumulative disadvantage. Indeed, the non-adjacent level model (M3) shows that, given equal attributes, women are 5.4% less likely than their male colleagues to be at head rather than first level. Finally, the group-level model (M4) reports a significant adjusted penalty, adding robustness to the previous models.

Table 2 – The gender gap in promotion

After having measured in which step of the ladder obstacles concentrate, their determinants were investigated. The nested model in Table 3 measures the contribution of gender difference in observed characteristics to the gender gap in promotion (analysis of differential characteristics). The results indicate that the main contribution to female disadvantage across the four models comes from (the gender difference in) work experience, while the rest of the controls do not seem to relevantly contribute to the gap: once they are added, the female coefficients barely change. This is not surprising, since very few observed factors besides experience explain anybody's chances of promotion (see Table A1 in the Appendix), except for salaried work hours (in M1, M3 and M4) and the sector. In consequence of this, even if men and women differ in some of these factors, it is irrelevant, because they do not make a difference in terms of promotion. When they do make a difference, either the gender difference is not enough to change the gap in promotion in a relevant way, as in the case of work hours¹⁴, or no gender difference occurs in the first place, as in the case of the sector (and therefore measuring the contribution of gender difference to the promotion gap is pointless).

Returning to work experience, this variable explains around one third of the unadjusted gender gap in M1, and around half in the remaining models. Moreover, when it is added in M2, it makes the female coefficient no longer significant. This suggests that, compared to men with similar experience, women do not experience a disadvantage in the probability of being head instead of vice. The variable measures the number of years since entry into the (medical) labor market and is strongly correlated with age (see Footnote 8). Its contribution in M2 suggests that women’s overall younger age—reflected in their concentration in the earliest cohorts—is the reason behind the persistence of an unadjusted promotion gap between vice and head level.

Table 3 – Nested models on rank: female coefficients

Once the contribution of the gender difference in observed characteristics was found, the mechanisms of discrimination were investigated. Discrimination occurs when the same characteristics in men and women are differently rewarded in terms of promotion. With this in mind, the four above-mentioned hypotheses were tested by including four interaction terms in the M1 and M3 models. Table 4 shows the marginal effects of these interaction terms. The interaction models M1_i and M3_i are reported in Table A2 of the Appendix.

With respect to sector (hypothesis 1), the results indicate that no significant disadvantage occurs for women in private institutions. On the contrary, in the private sector, women—like men—experience a significant premium in the cumulative probability of being head (M3_i). Women and men working in private hospitals are, respectively, 17.7% (column “Women”) and 16.3% (column “Men”) more likely to be head compared to their same-gendered counterparts in public hospitals. Furthermore, a significant gender gap in promotion (column “W-M”) occurs in public hospitals in both models (-7.3% and -5.8%), not in private ones.

With respect to specialty area (hypothesis 2), no clear indication of premium or penalty mechanism is apparent for women working in the female-dominated (medical) or male-dominated (surgical) areas compared to their female counterparts in the gender-balanced specialties of diagnostic and public health. However, a significant gender gap occurs in both models between male and female doctors working in the female-dominated medical area, but not in the male-dominated surgical area, which cautiously suggests that the latter is more gender equal than the former. More specifically, women are, respectively, 9.4% and 6.6% less likely than men to be vice (M1_i) or head (M3_i) in the medical

specialties, while no significant penalty is apparent in the surgical specialties.

With respect to marital status (hypothesis 3), results show that women do not experience a penalty related to marriage (or to cohabiting with a partner). On the contrary, having a spouse or cohabiting partner entails a positive, albeit insignificant, return for women in both models. At the same time, no clear evidence of a gender gap (“W-M”) is apparent, as the results are not consistent between the two models. In M1_i, because of the higher (non significant) male premium related to marriage, a gender gap between spouses persists in the likelihood of becoming vice. In M3_i, however, the gap occurs between single men and women, not between spouses.

With respect to parental status (hypothesis 4), no motherhood penalty occurs. On the contrary, the female marginal effect for having children, albeit insignificant, has a positive sign in both models. At the same time, a significant gender gap in promotion among parents persists (-8.9% in M1_i and -6.7% in M3_i), since the male premium for having children, however insignificant, is higher than the female. Mothers do not experience a penalty compared to their female colleagues with no children but they do when compared to their male colleagues with children, thanks to the higher male bonus related to parenthood. If negative discrimination against mothers has disappeared, positive discrimination toward fathers remains, which explains the persistence of a gender gap among parents.

Table 4 – Marginal effects of the interaction terms included in the interaction models M1_i and M3_i

Conclusions

This paper investigates the female disadvantage in promotion among doctors by analyzing a dataset of just over a thousand physicians working in Italy through logistic regressions. The purpose of this research has been twofold: to investigate at which step of the career ladder gender obstacles concentrate, and to identify the determinants of such obstacles.

Concerning the first research question, the results point toward women experiencing a significant disadvantage in promotion from first to vice level. Once they reach the vice level, this gender penalty seems to fall away. However, because of the mechanism of cumulative disadvantage, the penalties they face at the beginning of their careers have repercussions later on, translating into a significant disadvantage from first to head level. Contrary to the idea that gender obstacles suddenly appear in the

final ranks of the ladder—often associated with the glass ceiling principle—this research supports the sticky floors explanation of vertical segregation, suggesting that disadvantages appear at the beginning of the career ladder and keep accumulating from there.

These results are consistent with previous labor-market studies (Baxter and Wright 2000; Hultin 2003; Bihagen and Ohls 2006; Yap and Konrad 2009) and should be interpreted carefully. If women are subject to major obstacles in the transition from first to vice level, then the ones who make it through may be more qualified than their male counterparts. Therefore, the absence of female disadvantage from vice to head level may be a consequence of women in these ranks being more skilled and competent than their male colleagues, due to the more challenging selection process they have had to face in the previous step (Ferree and Purkayashka 2000). In other words, these results should not be taken as proof that women now have the same chances as men to reach the final step of the ladder, but rather as proof of a more adverse selection process occurring for them in the previous level. The presence of cumulative disadvantage, from first level to head, adds weight to this interpretation.

Concerning the second research question, analysis of the differential characteristics has shed light on the major role played by work experience, as well as age, in explaining women's promotion penalty, especially from vice to head level, since, once the relative control is added into the model, the gender gap is no longer significant. This suggests that the *unadjusted* penalty women face at the end of the career ladder is mainly due to demographic reasons, namely the lack of a sufficient number of women old enough to be in the pool of candidates for promotion to head. This is a hopeful message, cautiously suggesting that the current gender gap from vice to head level can not be ascribed to gender discrimination. In this vein, it would seem to be the case that it is only a matter of time before gender equality can be expected. However, the presence of an *adjusted* penalty at the beginning of the career ladder casts doubt on the equality experienced at the end of the hierarchy, since this likely follows on from a sharper selection process for women in the early stages, and is therefore not a true sign of real improvement in opportunities for women. This consideration finds further evidence in the analysis of differential returns.

In relation to this, two—rather unexpected—findings seem particularly relevant. First, women do not experience a maternity penalty. Second, the private sector is more gender equal than the public. Similar—albeit weaker—indications emerge from the analysis of the specialty area, cautiously suggesting the male-dominated surgical area is more gender equal than the female-dominated medical one. These results are consistent with previous studies, both in questioning the idea of a maternity

penalty among highly skilled women (Fox 2005; Perna 2005) and in suggesting that both the private sector (Bihagen and Ohls 2006) and male-dominated occupations/professions (England 1992; Hultin 2003) may be more gender equal than the public sector and female-dominated occupations/jobs.

These findings raise the issue of women self-selection and what this self-selection potentially costs them. Female doctors have striven to reduce the gender gap by matching their male colleagues' characteristics: they report only a small difference in work hours compared to men, while implementing strategies to reduce the motherhood penalty, including not having children, having few children, and outsourcing care and domestic work. From this perspective, the absence of a motherhood penalty should be ascribed to the fact that female doctors are a particularly career-oriented population who have succeeded in reducing their differences—in care responsibilities, and so in work hours—from men¹⁵. Men, however, do not seem to have gone through the equivalent change, since they do not take on a larger share of care and domestic work, while continuing to experience a fatherhood premium. This suggests that gender equality is being pursued primarily through women's efforts to fit into male-dominated organizations, rather than through men's involvement in unpaid work as long as the sexual division of labor within households remains substantially unchanged (Crompton 2006).

The findings related to sector and, more cautiously, to specialty, provide further empirical evidence for consideration. The efforts women have made to reduce the gender disadvantage are more palpable in private organizations and in the surgical area, both of which feature longer working hours and a higher percentage of women with no children¹⁶. At the same time, the private sector looks more gender equal than the public, in which the female population is more heterogeneous. In private organizations, many doctors are officially self-employed, and self-employed women are not entitled to the five months of maternity leave that are mandatory for contracted employees. Consequently, when caring for newborn children, they are likely to stay out of work for a shorter amount of time¹⁷. The likelihood of mothers coming back to work more quickly after giving birth, coupled with the fact that a higher proportion of women have no children, could be contributing to a reduction in statistical discrimination against women in the private sector. Faced with a lack of information concerning the lengths of maternity leave taken in private hospitals—which would have made it possible to test this hypothesis more appropriately—an analysis of the variation in parental returns by sector was undertaken (Section C of the Appendix). Results cautiously point toward the existence of a gender promotion gap among parents in public hospitals, but not private, thus providing empirical evidence for the above interpretation. Further investigation of this issue should be undertaken.

This research presents a few limiting factors. The first concerns the modest response rate (49%). This, however, has been partially offset by analysis of the representativity of the respondents. Second, no information is available on the lengths of maternity leave taken in private hospitals, which would have allowed to test the variation in maternity penalty across sectors. Third, the cross-sectional nature of the data do not allow to test whether significant changes have occurred across time. To do so, longitudinal data would be required.

Notwithstanding these limitations, this research suggests that gender discrimination is still an issue among doctors. At the same time, it has also thrown up positive results: no penalty seems to be occurring for women in the transition from vice to head level, nor for mothers, nor for women working in private hospitals or, more cautiously, the (male-dominated) surgical area. However, gender equality comes with a price: and that is the price of selection. Only a limited group of women—those who can sufficiently reduce their gender difference with men—seem to experience equal opportunities. When women, as a group, become more heterogeneous, gender equality is unlikely to be achieved. These results reveal the costs of gender equality, in terms of women's effort and in relation to equality among women.

Tables

Table 1 – Mean differences by characteristics

	Men	Women	T-Test
Age	52.29	47.89	0.0000
Grade	107.12	108.01	0.0004
Honors	45.1	51.5	0.0468
Work experience (years)	21.62	17.1	0.0000
Training abroad (months)	5.20	2.80	0.0004
Public sector	81.56	84.07	0.2759
Work hours (h/w):	47.78	44.97	0.0000
Salaried work hours (h/w)	44.0	42.9	0.0467
Private practice hours (h/w)	3.74	2.04	0.0000
Contract type:			
Open-ended	78.4	74.1	0.0974
Freelance	15.0	12.7	0.279
Atypical	6.5	13.1	0.0003
Specialty area:			
Medicine	40.2	57.0	0.0000
Surgery	35.4	16.2	0.0000
Diagnostic	21.4	24.2	0.2659
Public health	3.1	2.5	0.581
Rank/level:			
First	50.63	70.25	0.0000
Vice	28.57	18.62	0.0001
Head	18.81	6.14	0.0000
All others	1.99	4.99	0.0070
Annual income (euro)	85,973.03	62,747.42	0.0000
Cohabiting partner or spouse:	86.4	73.7	0.0000
Cohabiting partner	15.91	15.74	0.9378
Spouse	70.52	57.97	0.0000
Children:	76.1	61.0	0.0000
Number of children	1.51	1.06	0.0000
Care and domestic work (h/w)	15.53	25.48	0.0000
Outsourced care and domestic work (h/w)	5.75	6.95	0.0000

Note: the variables “grade”, “honors”, “contract type” and “specialty area” include a few missing cases. For these variables, the analyses reported in the table have been performed on 979 observations (for grade and honors), 1,070 (for contract type) and 1,060 (for specialty area). The analyses of all the remaining variables have been performed on the total number of respondents (1,074).

Table 2 - The gender gap in promotion

		Unadjusted			Adjusted		
		b	d/dx	N	b	dy/dx	N
M1	Vice vs First	-0.841***	-0.158***	840	-0.529**	-0.082**	840
M2	Head vs Vice	-0.738**	-0.161**	339	-0.349	-0.057	339
M3	Head vs First	-1.579***	-0.197***	747	-0.777*	-0.054*	747
M4	Head vs all others	-1.364***	-0.136***	963	-0.661*	-0.047*	963

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

Note: this table reports the female coefficient, in logit (b) and marginal effect (dy/dx), of four logit models. The dependent variable (DV) is the position held by the respondent. The four models differ in the way the DV is coded, as well as in the size of the dataset. In M1, the DV is coded as a dummy variable where 1 = vice and 0 = first level. In M2, 1 = head and 0 = vice. In M3, 1 = head and 0 = first level. In M4, 1 = head and 0 = all other levels (first and vice). The adjusted models include controls for human capital, work and family characteristics. A detailed description of the measures is included in the paragraph “Models and Measures”, while the coefficients of the controls can be viewed in Table A1 of the Appendix.

Table 3 – Nested models on rank: female coefficients

			M1	M2	M3	M4
			Vice vs first	Head vs vice	Head vs first	Head vs all others
1	Gender (unadjusted gap)	b	-0.841***	-0.738**	-1.579***	-1.364***
		dy/dx	-0.158***	-0.161**	-0.197***	-0.136***
2	+ Work control 1: experience	b	-0.655***	-0.438	-1.100***	-0.844***
		dy/dx	-0.107***	-0.083	-0.096***	-0.068***
3	+ Work control 2: work hours	b	-0.605***	-0.368	-1.069***	-0.778**
		dy/dx	-0.096**	-0.069	-0.087***	-0.062**
4	+ Work control 3: sector, contract type, and specialty	b	-0.553**	-0.453	-1.006***	-0.802**
		dy/dx	-0.091**	-0.076	-0.077***	-0.059**
5	+ Human capital: education and training	b	-0.591**	-0.373	-1.010**	-0.756**
		dy/dx	-0.093**	-0.062	-0.073**	-0.055**
6	+ Family control: marital and parental status	b	-0.488*	-0.396	-0.881**	-0.711*
		dy/dx	-0.076*	-0.066	-0.063**	-0.051**
7	+ Work-life arrangements: unpaid and outsourced work	b	-0.529**	-0.349	-0.777*	-0.661*
		dy/dx	-0.082**	-0.057	-0.054**	-0.047*
N			840	339	747	963

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

Note: this table reports the female coefficient in logit (b) and marginal effect (dy/dx). The first row reports the unadjusted gender promotion gap. The following rows progressively add specific variables or sets of variables. Work hours include both salaried work hours and hours of private practice. The last row reports the adjusted gender promotion gap. The full models are reported in Table A1 of the Appendix.

Table 4 - Marginal effects of the interaction terms included in Models M1_1 and M3_i

	M1_i: vice vs first level						M3_i: head vs first level					
	Men		Women		W-M		Men		Women		W-M	
Private hospital: no	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.073*	(0.025)	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.058*	(0.018)
Private hospital: yes	0.133	(0.077)	0.080	(0.241)	-0.126	(0.145)	0.163**	(0.002)	0.177**	(0.002)	-0.043	(0.498)
Specialty: diagnostic + public health	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.099	(0.072)	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.018	(0.677)
Specialty: medicine	-0.027	(0.589)	-0.023	(0.661)	-0.094*	(0.024)	-0.016	(0.657)	0.064	(0.067)	-0.066*	(0.020)
Specialty: surgery	-0.022	(0.609)	0.042	(0.527)	-0.034	(0.606)	0.005	(0.894)	-0.049	(0.374)	-0.072	(0.181)
Spouse or cohabiting partner: no	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.015	(0.828)	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.113*	(0.018)
Spouse or cohabiting partner: yes	0.105	(0.103)	0.026	(0.586)	-0.095**	(0.008)	-0.019	(0.645)	0.053	(0.102)	-0.041	(0.125)
Children: no	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.056	(0.327)	0	(.)	0	(.)	-0.032	(0.434)
Children: yes	0.056	(0.306)	0.023	(0.621)	-0.089*	(0.019)	0.060	(0.113)	0.025	(0.471)	-0.067*	(0.020)

p-values in parenthesis: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Note: this table shows the differences in the predicted margins (partial changes) for men, women, and between men and women, with respect to the variables reported in the first column. The table is based on the interaction models M1_i and M3_i, reported in Table A2 of the Appendix. In both models, the variable gender (0 = man; 1 = woman) is interacted with the variables sector (0 = public; 1 = private), specialty (0 = diagnostic and public health; 1 = medicine; 2 = surgery), spouse or cohabiting partner (0 = no; 1 = yes), and children (0 = no; 1 = yes). Marginal effects on the interaction terms are then computed. The dependent variable is a dummy, based on the position held by the respondent: in M1_i, 1 = vice and 0 = first level, and in M3_i 1 = head and 0 = first.

About the Author

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Footnotes

1. The distinction between micro meso and macro levels is only one of many conceptual frameworks that could have been used. A more common way to explain inequalities—in career progression and, more often, in pay—is to distinguish between supply and demand-side factors. In its original, and strictest, sense, this distinction refers to individual explanations, that is, on the one side (supply), the difference in characteristics between female and male workers, and on the other (demand), the employer’s discrimination against women. Reflecting the need to go beyond the individual dimension of inequalities (Reskin 1993; Blau and Kahn 2017), some authors either drop the terminology of supply and demand (for example, Olsen and Walby 2004) or they stretch the meaning of the term “demand” beyond employer’s individual bias, to embrace more contextual factors, such as the organization, the structure of the labor market and policies (for example, Gabaldon et al. 2016).

2. Differences in characteristics reflect differences in choices. The notion of choice, however, is not unproblematic. Both neoclassical economic and socialization theories argue that choices reflect men’s and women’s *preferences*. However, where the former emphasizes women’s lower investment in human capital as a knock-on effect of their expectation that family obligations will limit their work (Mincer & Polachek 1974), the latter focuses on interiorized gender expectations leading women to make family-friendly work choices (for a review of sex-role socialization theories, see Marini and Briton 1984). By contrast, more recent and critical accounts have emphasized the role of *structural constraints* in affecting choices. These include, for example, systematic disadvantage in organizations and indirect discrimination (Olsen and Walby, 2004).

3. This distinction should be considered carefully for two reasons. First, studies based on observational data can hardly account for characteristics that are difficult to observe (productivity, motivation, ability). In consequence of this, the part of the gap attributed to discrimination may be either underestimated (if women are, on average, more productive, motivated, and/or skilled than men), or overestimated (if the contrary were to be true). This is why the “remuneration” component—the part of the gap remaining after controlling for differences in characteristics—is also called the “unexplained” component of the gap, since it includes employer discrimination (occurring when the same observed characteristics are differently “remunerated”) but also unobserved factors. Second, gender differences in observable characteristics may be affected by indirect discrimination (Olsen and Walby 2004) through the mechanism of “feedback effects” (Grimshaw and Rubery 2002). For example, medical school professors might “dissuade” their female students from entering traditionally male specialties such as surgery (McManus and Sproston 2000). Once in the labor market, women may find themselves being overlooked by their employers for training programs (Grimshaw and Rubery 2002). Inappropriate working conditions, the lack of access to informal networking and the lack of a mentor may also affect women’s motivation and choices (Kelly and Grant 2012). Therefore, differences in characteristics between men and women should never be considered as evidence for legitimizing inequalities, since they may, at least partly, be due to indirect discrimination.

4. The five hospitals surveyed for this research include the “Policlinico” in Milan, the Civil Hospital in Legnano, the Sant’Anna Hospital in Como, the San Donato Hospital in San Donato, and a fifth hospital which has asked to remain anonymous. The first three organizations are public providers, while the last two are private. Hospitals will be mentioned in the paper as follows: Public 1 = Policlinico; Public 2 = Legnano; Public 3 = Como; Private 1 = San Donato; and Private 2 = Anonymous.

5. The response rate varies between the hospitals: 43.6% from Public 1; 56.7% from Public 2; 48% from Public 3; 39.2% from Private 1; and 50.3% from Private 2.

6. Data provided by the Regional Health Department, available upon request.

7. The first level of the harmonized scale includes thirty-seven cases that are difficult to code: collaborators (co.co.co.), grant holders, public hospital freelancers, and purely academic researchers. Because of the similarities in characteristics with first level doctors (in salary, age, tasks, and responsibilities), these cases were included in the first level of the scale used in all the models, in Figure 1 (text) and Figure D1 (online appendix) while in Table 1 they are included in the item “all others”.

8. The variables “experience” and “age” are highly correlated (Pearson’s r : 0.9497), and the models are consistent, regardless of which is used as the variable. However, given the purpose of this study, experience was preferred, since it gives account of the number of years an individual has been working.

9. Doctors may use hospital spaces and facilities for their private practice, in return for passing on an agreed share of their private practice income to the hospital.

10. Doctors with freelance “contracts” are formally self-employed (using the so-called “partita IVA”), and they issue an invoice to the hospital. The amount on the invoice, as well as the number of weekly hours worked, is defined by a contract with the hospital. This type of contract should not be confused with an agreement defining the limits of private practice, which is something physicians perform outside their (salaried or invoice-based) working hours. Freelance contracts are concentrated in private hospitals, where 67% of doctors have this type of contract, vs 3% in public hospitals.

11. As such, they are the difference, for a unit change, in the predicted margins. For this reason, they are also called “partial changes”. Partial changes—or differences in the predicted margins—can be marginal (as in the case of continuous independent variables dy/dx) or discrete (in the case of categorical variables $\Delta y/\Delta x$) (Scott Long and Freese 2006). However, the term discrete is rarely used in the literature in reference to changes in categorical variables. In its place, the term marginal is widely employed. The same holds true for the term effect: regression-based analysis on observational data cannot prove a causal relationship between the independent and dependent variables. For this reason, the term effect is misleading. However, it is widely used in the literature as well. Because of the consolidated use of the terms “marginal” and “effect”, I will continue to use them, being aware that they are a slight abuse of terminology.

12. This explains why, given the equation $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 Z + \beta_3 XZ + \epsilon$, it is possible for the marginal effect of a unit change in X on Y , when the modifying variable $Z = 1$, to be significant even if the coefficient of the interaction term in the regression model is not (see: Brambor et al. 2015).

13. Before analyzing the dataset, its representativity was tested by analyzing differences in attributes between respondents and non-respondents through one-sample t-tests. The analyses were undertaken on the basis of the information provided by each hospital on its physicians. Public 1 provided the gender, rank, year of birth, and gross income of its doctors; Public 2 the gender, type of practice, specialty, rank, and seniority; Public 3 the gender, type of practice, and specialty; Private 1 the gender, type of practice, rank, specialty, and age; and Private 2 the gender and contract type. The only common information provided was the gender distribution of doctors: 53.6% men and 46.4% women across the five hospitals, compared with the respective 51.5% and 49.5% among respondents (p value: 0.1649). As for the remaining characteristics, representativity tests were undertaken hospital by hospital. No significant gender differences (between respondents and non-respondents) were found, except for a slight underrepresentation of freelance and head doctors in Public 2, and an overrepresentation of doctors in the medical specialty in Public 3.

14. The gender difference in hours entails a small variation—around one percentage point across all models—in the female coefficients in Table 3. However, its contribution should be considered carefully. Work hours were measured simultaneously with rank, and therefore may be a consequence of the doctor’s current position, rather than a determinant. As such, their inclusion in the model entails a

problem of reverse causality, due to the cross-sectional nature of the data. To account for this issue, the same models were run without work hours. No relevant changes were observed, and therefore work hours were kept as control to avoid the risk of model misspecification: work hours are a proxy of the commitment to the organization (in the case of salaried work hours) or to the profession in general (in the case of private practice hours), and they make it possible to compare men and women who are the most similar in this respect.

15. Table 3 shows that work-life arrangements—including the hours of domestic and care work (unpaid work) and hours of domestic and care work outsourced to others —can reduce the gender gap by around 0.5-2 percentage points, depending on the model. By adding the two variables separately (analysis available upon request), results show that the reduction in the gap is due primarily to the contribution of care and domestic work outsourced, while unpaid work only marginally increases—or doesn't even affect—the female coefficient.

16. Doctors work 49 hours per week in private hospitals and 48 in the surgical area, compared to 46 hours in the public sector and medical area respectively. The percentage of women with no children is 49% in private organizations (vs 37% in public), and 45% in the surgical area (vs 40% in the medical area).

17. Qualitative insights suggest that women in the private sector tend to take less time off after giving birth. This understanding stems from a parallel qualitative research field, in which 25 people—including key experts, doctors, and residents—were interviewed, and four institutional meetings with health care managers and doctors were held in order to disseminate the preliminary results of this research.

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